

MEANS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL INFLUENCE IN COMMUNICATION

Abduvaliyeva Shalola Sadriddinovna

Foreign language teacher for lawyers
of the "General Education" department
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10512526>

Abstract. Communication is commonly characterized as the transmission of data. Its exact definition is debated and there are differences almost whether inadvertent or fizzled transmissions are included and whether communication not as it were transmits meaning but moreover makes it. Models of communication are rearranged outlines of its primary components and their intelligent. This article describes about means of psychological influence in communication.

Keywords: Communication, psychology, verbal influence, nonverbal influence, paralinguistic influence.

Communication – is the main form of interpersonal relations, with the help of which people communicate with each other mentally, exchange information, influence each other, feel and understand each other. .Muloqot – orqali insonlar bir-birlariga ta’sir etadilar. [4.261] In the dictionary of psychology, the concept of communication is given two different definitions:

1. Communication - the process of establishing and developing communication related to the need for cooperative activity;
2. Communication - interaction of subjects through the system of signs.

[1.97]

Communication is a multifaceted process of the development of connections between people arising from the needs of joint activity. Communication includes the exchange of information between the participants. This takes into account the communicative aspect of the relationship. People turn to language first when entering into a relationship. Another aspect of communication is the mutual action of the participants in the relationship - in the process of speech, they exchange not only words, but also actions. [1.98] Communication is understood as the exchange of ideas or information by people through speaking, writing and other actions. [3.371]

Psychological influence in communication is the ability to influence the thoughts, feelings and behavior of people using various means. Three means of psychological influence are distinguished:

Verbal influence is the influence we show through our words and speech. Words are the main tools in this. Speech is a process of mutual communication,

the tool of which is words. In both monologic speech and dialogic speech, a person wants to influence his partner by finding the most effective words, using all his vocabulary.

Paralinguistic influence is the surrounding factors that disturb the speech, strengthen it or weaken it. This includes high or low speech, articulation, sounds, pauses, stuttering, coughing, tongue movements, exclamations. Depending on this, for example, if our friend promises us something, we will know how sincere he is. We believe that he will say "Of course I will!" with an open face and a bold voice.

The meaning of **non-verbal influence** is "without speech". This includes the positions of the interlocutors in relation to each other, situations (close, distant, intimate), gestures, facial expressions, pantomimes, looks, direct feelings of each other, external appearance, various signals (noise, smells) coming out of it. All of them enhance the communication process and help the interlocutors to get to know each other better. For example, if in the first minutes of the meeting your friend turns around without looking at you and says, "I'm glad to see you," would you believe it? [2.164]

When people communicate with each other, one of their main goals is to influence each other, i.e. to persuade them to their ideas, to call them to action, to change their instructions. and to make a good impression.

V. Karimova also distinguishes three means of psychological influence in psychology, as mentioned above:

- 1) Verbal influence;
- 2) Paralinguistic influence;
- 3) Non-verbal influence. [1.98]

A characteristic thing in the communication process is that when the interlocutors want to influence each other, they first think about what to say and what words to influence. In fact, those words and actions around them play an important role.

According to the American scientist Megrabyan's formula, 7% of spoken words, 38% of paralinguistic factors, and 58% of non-verbal actions affect positive impressions of interlocutors who are meeting for the first time. [2.164]

Therefore, in the process of communication, people can exchange information or influence each other not only through words, but also through their behavior, body movements, various gestures. Therefore, the influence of people on each other is different for different people, and this is a very complicated phenomenon.

References:

1. M.Maxsudova “Muloqot psixologiyasi” o’quv qo’llanma, T.: “TURON-IQBOL” – 2006, 117 b
2. V.Karimova “Psixologiya” (Abdulla Qodiriy nomidagi xalq merosi nashriyoti) T.: 2002, 203 b
3. “The New Oxford Dictionary of English” Edited by: Judy Pearsall Oxford University press
4. Abduhakim o’g’li, Abdullayev Asqar. "Challenges in Teaching Writing to Young Learners." Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development 2.3 (2023): 14-16.
5. Abdullayev A., Imansyah A. THE WAYS OF WORD-FORMATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE //Current approaches and new research in modern sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – С. 5-9.
6. Abdullayev A. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 26. – С. 5-8.
7. В.М.Umarov “Psixologiya” T.: “Voris-nashriyot” – 2012, 271b

